

To Estimate High Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol/hs-C Reactive Protein Ratio in Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction (HFpEF)Aparna Divakaran¹, Hardayal Meena², Harish Chandra Barjatya³, Harpreet Singh Brahm⁴^{1,4}PG Resident, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)²Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)³Senior professor and Unit Head, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)

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Abstract:**Background:** Heart Failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) represents approximately 50% of heart failure cases and poses unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Inflammation plays a crucial role in HFpEF pathogenesis, but reliable biomarkers remain limited. This study evaluates the relationship between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function in HFpEF patients.**Methods:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study enrolled 113 patients with HFpEF (EF \geq 50%) at J.L.N Hospital, Ajmer from December 2022 to November 2023. We measured HDL-C and hs-CRP levels and correlated their ratio with comprehensive echocardiographic parameters including LVEF, LAV, and TAPSE, following standardized protocols.**Results:** Our study analyzed 113 patients with HFpEF, with males comprising 63.7% of the population. Age distribution showed predominance in the 51-60 years group (36.3%), followed by 41-50 years (31.0%). Major risk factors included hypertension (67.26%), alcoholism (54.87%), and diabetes (46.90%). Dyspnea was the most common presenting symptom (86.7%), with basal lung crepitations being the predominant sign (92.04%). Laboratory findings revealed median hs-CRP of 3.2 mg/dl (IQR: 2.5-4.1) with 54.87% patients showing moderate elevation (1-3 mg/dl). HDL levels were predominantly low, with median 34 mg/dl (IQR: 29-47) and 68.14% patients in 30-39 mg/dl range. Mean HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio was 4.31 \pm 0.96. Echocardiographic assessment showed preserved systolic function (median LVEF 59%, IQR: 56-67%) with evidence of diastolic dysfunction (E/e' median 15, IQR: 13-22). Multiple regression analysis demonstrated significant correlations between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function parameters: LVEF (β =-0.087, p =0.048), LAV & LVMI index (β =-0.081, p =0.032), and TAPSE (β =0.079, p =0.041). NYHA classification revealed predominantly advanced disease with 87.61% patients in Class III/IV.**Conclusion:** The HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio demonstrates significant correlation with cardiac function parameters in HFpEF patients, suggesting its potential as a novel prognostic marker.**Keywords:** Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction, High-density lipoprotein, High-sensitivity C-reactive protein, Cardiac function, Biomarkers.

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Introduction

Heart Failure (HF) represents a major global health challenge affecting approximately 64 million individuals worldwide [1]. The current understanding recognizes HF as a complex clinical syndrome characterized by structural and/or functional cardiac abnormalities leading to reduced cardiac output or elevated filling pressures [2-4]. In 2021, a universal definition proposed characterizing HF based on structural or functional cardiac abnormalities resulting in symptoms supported by elevated natri-

uretic peptide levels [5]. Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) accounts for about 50% of all heart failure cases[6,7], characterized by normal left ventricular ejection fraction (\geq 50%) but impaired diastolic function[8]. The prevalence is particularly high among older adults and those with comorbidities like obesity, diabetes, dyslipidemia, and hypertension [9]. In the United States alone, approximately 3 million individuals are affected by HFpEF [10]. Recent evidence sug-

gests chronic inflammation linked to cardiovascular risk factors plays a primary role in declining diastolic function [11]. This inflammatory state affects multiple cellular pathways, leading to myocardial stiffness and diastolic dysfunction [12-14]. High-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) has emerged as a reliable inflammatory marker [15], with elevated levels correlating with worse vascular outcomes and increased left ventricular filling pressures in coronary artery disease patients [16,17]. High-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) has been recognized as a protective factor against cardiovascular disease [18]. The Framingham Study demonstrated low HDL-C levels correlate with increased morbidity in both heart failure and coronary heart disease [19,20]. HDL functions as a scavenger, clearing accumulated cholesterol from macrophages and reducing inflammation through multiple mechanisms [21,22]. Recent research suggests combining these markers provides more comprehensive insights than either alone. Luo et al. demonstrated that elevated hs-CRP to HDL-C ratio may reflect both inflammatory activity and dyslipidemia in coronary artery disease [23]. Another study found the HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio closely correlates with left ventricular diastolic function in the absence of significant coronary atherosclerosis [24]. Despite these promising findings, the relationship between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function in HFpEF remains poorly understood, particularly in our geographic region. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate this relationship and assess its potential as a novel prognostic marker in HFpEF patients.

Methodology

This hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Ajmer, following institutional ethical committee approval. The study period extended from December 2022 to November 2023, enrolling 113 patients based on sample size calculation using the formula $n = z^2 pq / d^2$, where $z = 1.96$ (95% confidence interval), $p =$ assumed probability, and $d =$ precision margin. Patient selection followed strict criteria based on Framingham's diagnostic guidelines for heart failure. Inclusion required patients presenting with acute decompensated heart failure (meeting at least two major or one major plus two minor Framingham criteria) and having preserved ejection fraction ($\geq 50\%$) on echocardiography.

We excluded patients with reduced ejection fraction ($< 50\%$), severe valvular disease (aortic stenosis/ regurgitation, mitral stenosis/regurgitation), structural cardiac abnormalities, cor pulmonale, renal failure, pulmonary hypertension, age below 18 years, acute coronary syndrome, poor 6-month prognosis from non-cardiac diseases, and those taking medications affecting CRP or HDL-C levels

(including antipsychotics, statins, ACE inhibitors, and antidiabetic agents).

All enrolled patients underwent comprehensive clinical evaluation following standardized protocols. This included detailed history taking, thorough physical examination, and extensive laboratory investigations.

Blood samples were collected after overnight fasting for lipid profile analysis. HDL-C was measured using a fully automated analyzer AU 700 employing spectrophotometry principles. hs-CRP was measured using semi-automated analyzer MAG-LUMI 800 based on chemiluminescence, with values categorized as < 1 , 1-3, and > 3 mg/L representing low, moderate, and high risk respectively.

Transthoracic echocardiography was performed within one week of admission using Sonoline G-50, Siemens real-time sector scanner with 3.5Hz convex transducer probe. Key measurements included left ventricular ejection fraction (using modified Simpson's method), left ventricular diastolic and systolic diameters, interventricular septum thickness, left atrial volume, and tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion (TAPSE). Left ventricular mass was calculated using linear methods following standard formulae.

The HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio was calculated as HDL-C (mmol/L)/hs-CRP (mg/L). Statistical analysis employed SPSS version 25.0, with data presented as mean \pm SD or median with interquartile range as appropriate. Multiple regression analysis assessed correlations between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac parameters, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Additional verification used ANOVA methodology.

Results

The study included 113 patients presenting with acute decompensated heart failure based on Framingham's criteria and preserved ejection fraction ($\geq 50\%$). The study subjects were distributed according to gender and age. Majority of the subjects were males ($n = 72$, 63.7%) while females constituted 36.3% ($n = 41$) of the study population.

Most of the study subjects were within 51-60 years of age ($n = 41$, 36.3%), followed by 35 (31.0%) who were between 41-50 years of age. There were 14 (12.4%) subjects between 31-40 years, 3 (2.7%) subjects were between 21-30 years of age and 20 (17.7%) were > 60 years of age. Risk factors assessment showed that majority of subjects had hypertension ($n = 76$, 67.26%). Other risk factors included alcoholism (54.87%), diabetes (46.90%), smoking (46.02%), dyslipidaemia (33.63%), obesity (13.27%) and history of COVID (25.6%). Clinical presentation revealed that majority of subjects showed symptom of dyspnoea ($n = 98$, 86.7%). Pedal oedema, orthopnoea and abdomen distension

was revealed in 59.3%, 54.9% and 33.6% of subjects respectively. Physical examination showed basal lung crepitations as most common sign (n=104, 92.04%) while peripheral oedema, raised

JVP, gallop, ascites, pleural effusion and enlarged tender liver was revealed in 54.87%, 46.90%, 33.63%, 17.70%, 13.27% and 10.62% of subjects respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Population (N=113)

Characteristic	Number (%)
Gender	
Male	72 (63.7%)
Female	41 (36.3%)
Age Groups (years)	
21-30	3 (2.7%)
31-40	14 (12.4%)
41-50	35 (31.0%)
51-60	41 (36.3%)
>60	20 (17.7%)
Risk Factors	
Hypertension	76 (67.26%)
Alcoholism	62 (54.87%)
Diabetes	53 (46.90%)
Smoking	52 (46.02%)
Dyslipidemia	38 (33.63%)
Obesity	15 (13.27%)
History of COVID	29 (25.6%)
Clinical Presentation	
Dyspnea	98 (86.7%)
Orthopnea	62 (54.9%)
Pedal Edema	67 (59.3%)
Abdomen Distension	38 (33.6%)

Table 2: Investigative Profile

Variables	Median	IQR
WBC ($10^9/L$)	6.9	5.1-9.2
Hb (g/dl)	11.2	8.6-12.8
LDL (mmol/l)	2.2	1.5-2.6
Cholesterol (mmol/l)	3.98	3.4-4.7
TGL (mmol/l)	0.9	0.7-1.3
Pro BNP (pg/ml)	850	2240

The investigative profile revealed several significant patterns in the study population. Hematological parameters showed moderate anemia with median hemoglobin of 11.2 g/dl and normal white cell counts (median $6.9 \times 10^9/L$). The lipid profile demonstrated relatively low LDL and total cholesterol levels, with medians of 2.2 mmol/l and 3.98

mmol/l respectively, possibly reflecting the chronic disease state. Pro BNP levels were markedly elevated (median 850 pg/ml), confirming the diagnosis of heart failure. These findings collectively suggest metabolic alterations characteristic of chronic heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (Table 2).

Table 3: Inflammatory and Lipid Parameters

Parameter	Number (%)
hs-CRP (mg/dl)	
<1	27 (23.89)
1-3	62 (54.87)
>3	24 (21.24)
Median (IQR)	3.2 (2.5-4.1)
HDL (mg/dl)	
<30	18 (15.93)
30-39	77 (68.14)
40-49	16 (14.16)

50-59	2 (1.77)
Median (IQR)	34 (29-47)
Mean HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio	4.31±0.96

The inflammatory and lipid profiles demonstrated significant patterns characteristic of HFpEF. The majority of patients (54.87%) showed moderate elevation in hs-CRP (1-3 mg/dl), with median value of 3.2 mg/dl, indicating ongoing systemic inflammation. HDL levels were predominantly in the lower range, with 68.14% of patients having values

between 30-39 mg/dl and median of 34 mg/dl, suggesting compromised cardio protective mechanisms. The mean HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio was 4.31±0.96, providing a composite measure of both inflammatory and lipid status. These findings support the concept of HFpEF as an inflammatory-metabolic disorder (Table 3).

Table 4: Echocardiographic Parameters

Variables	Median	IQR
LVDd (mm)	47	40-54
LVDs (mm)	31	25-35
IVSTd (mm)	11	9-12
LVPWTd (mm)	11	9-12
LADs (mm)	45	38-50
LVEF (%)	59	56-67
E/e' (septal)	15	13-22
TAPSE (mm)	16	15-20
Left Atrial Volume (ml)	71	55-68
IVCD (mm)	14	12-17

The echocardiographic findings revealed preserved systolic function with evidence of diastolic dysfunction.

Left ventricular ejection fraction was preserved (median 59%, IQR 56-67%), while E/e' ratio was elevated (median 15, IQR 13-22), indicating impaired diastolic function. Left atrial enlargement

(median volume 71 ml) and increased wall thickness (IVSTd and LVPWTd both 11 mm) suggested chronic diastolic dysfunction. TAPSE measurements (median 16 mm) indicated relatively preserved right ventricular function. These parameters collectively confirm the diagnosis of HFpEF with significant structural remodeling (Table 4).

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis and Correlation with Cardiac Function

Variables	Standard β coefficient	p value
LVEF	-0.087	0.048*
LAV & LVMI Index	-0.081	0.032*
TAPSE	0.079	0.041*

*statistically significant

Multiple regression analysis revealed significant correlations between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function parameters.

LVEF showed a negative correlation (β =-0.087, p =0.048), suggesting that lower HDL-C/hs-CRP ratios are associated with higher ejection fractions within the preserved range. The product of LAV and LVMI, used as an index of left ventricular diastolic function, demonstrated a significant negative

correlation (β =-0.081, p =0.032), indicating that lower ratios correlate with worse diastolic function. TAPSE showed a positive correlation (β =0.079, p =0.041), suggesting that higher HDL-C/hs-CRP ratios are associated with better right ventricular function.

These findings support the potential utility of HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio as a marker of both left and right ventricular function in HFpEF patients (Table 5).

Table 6: NYHA Classification Distribution

NYHA Class	Number of Patients	Percentage
I	4	3.53
II	10	8.85
III	38	33.63
IV	61	53.98
Total	113	100

The distribution of NYHA functional classes revealed that majority of patients presented with advanced symptoms. More than half the patients (53.98%) were in NYHA Class IV, indicating symptoms at rest, while another third (33.63%) were in Class III, showing symptoms with mild activity. Only 12.38% patients were in NYHA Classes I and II combined, suggesting that most patients present late in their disease course. This distribution also correlates with the inflammatory and cardiac parameters, indicating that higher NYHA classes are associated with more severe pathophysiological derangements (Table 6).

Discussion

The present study provides comprehensive insights into the relationship between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function in HFpEF patients. Our demographic analysis revealed significant patterns that align with current understanding of HFpEF epidemiology. The male predominance (63.7%) with peak age in 51-60 years (36.3%) mirrors findings from Bhatia RS et al.[25], who reported similar gender distributions in HFpEF populations. Tsuchihashi-Makaya M et al.[26] also noted comparable age-related patterns, strengthening the representativeness of our study population.

The risk factor profile in our study was particularly noteworthy with hypertension (67.26%), diabetes (46.90%), and smoking (46.02%) emerging as predominant comorbidities. This pattern aligns closely with Paulus WJ et al.[27] seminal work describing the inflammatory-metabolic paradigm of HFpEF pathogenesis. The significant proportion of patients with dyslipidemia (33.63%) and history of COVID (25.6%) adds to emerging evidence about metabolic and post-viral contributions to HFpEF development.

Laboratory findings demonstrated a complex interplay of inflammatory and metabolic markers. The elevation in Pro BNP levels (median 850 pg/ml) confirms heart failure diagnosis, corresponding with diagnostic criteria established by Masugata H et al.[28]. The pattern of hs-CRP elevation, with 54.87% of patients showing levels between 1-3 mg/dl, strongly supports Koller L et al.[29] observations about the inflammatory burden in HFpEF. Kim JB et al.[30] previously demonstrated impaired anti-inflammatory properties of HDL in heart failure, which aligns with our finding of predominantly low HDL levels (68.14% between 30-39 mg/dl).

The echocardiographic profile revealed sophisticated patterns of cardiac remodeling. While LVEF was preserved (median 59%), evidence of diastolic dysfunction was clear through elevated E/e' ratios (median 15). These findings support DuBrock HM et al.[31] work on structural adaptations in HFpEF. The increased left atrial volume (median 71 ml) and wall thickness measurements provide objective

evidence of chronic diastolic dysfunction as previously described by Tang X et al.[32].

The correlation analysis yielded particularly valuable insights. The HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio showed significant relationships with multiple cardiac parameters, supporting Yano M et al.[33] findings about its potential prognostic value. The negative correlation with LVEF ($\beta=-0.087$, $p=0.048$) and LAV & LVMI index ($\beta=-0.081$, $p=0.032$) suggests this ratio might serve as an integrated marker of cardiac remodeling. The positive correlation with TAPSE ($\beta=0.079$, $p=0.041$) extends Han E et al.[34] observations about right ventricular function assessment in heart failure.

The NYHA classification distribution in our study population provides critical clinical context. The predominance of advanced classes (87.61% in Class III/IV) aligns with Chevli PA et al.[35] observations about typical presentation patterns in HFpEF. This finding gains additional significance when considered alongside Yao SM et al.[36] work linking inflammatory markers to functional status.

The combined analysis of HDL-C and hs-CRP offers unique insights into the inflammatory-metabolic axis in HFpEF. Bafei SEC et al.[37] previously demonstrated the interaction between inflammation and lipid metabolism in cardiovascular disease, which our findings extend specifically to HFpEF. Feng G et al.[38] work on combined inflammatory-metabolic markers provides a theoretical framework supporting our observations.

Recent research by Gao Y et al.[39] has demonstrated the broader cardiovascular implications of HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio. Our results build upon this foundation, specifically demonstrating its utility in HFpEF patients. The strong correlations with established cardiac parameters support Sun L et al.[40] suggestions about potential therapeutic monitoring applications.

Conclusion

This comprehensive study demonstrates significant correlations between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and cardiac function parameters in HFpEF patients, suggesting its potential utility as a novel prognostic marker. Our findings reveal that this ratio correlates with both left and right ventricular function indices, making it a potentially valuable tool for comprehensive patient assessment. The strong associations with established markers of diastolic dysfunction, including E/e' ratio and left atrial volume, suggest its potential role in early disease detection and monitoring.

The relationship between HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio and NYHA functional class further supports its clinical relevance, potentially offering an objective measure to complement subjective symptom assessment. The significant correlations with multiple cardiac parameters suggest that this ratio might reflect the

complex pathophysiological processes underlying HFpEF, including both inflammatory and metabolic components. This integrated approach to disease assessment aligns with contemporary understanding of HFpEF as a multifaceted syndrome rather than a simple mechanical disorder of diastolic function. Future research directions should focus on longitudinal studies to establish the predictive value of HDL-C/hs-CRP ratio for clinical outcomes, multi-center validation to establish definitive cut-off values, and investigation of therapeutic interventions targeting both inflammatory and lipid pathways. The potential utility of this ratio in guiding treatment decisions and monitoring therapeutic response also merits exploration. These findings contribute to our understanding of HFpEF pathophysiology and suggest potential new approaches to patient assessment and monitoring, though further validation studies are needed before widespread clinical implementation.

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